

**TOPICAL ISSUES OF INCREASING LEGAL CONSCIOUSNESS AND
LEGAL CULTURE****Burxonov Shoxruxbek Shuxratbek o'g'li**

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur tezis huquqiy ong va huquqiy madaniyatni oshirishning dolzarb masalalariga hamda huquqiy ong va huquqiy madaniyat bilan bog'liq holda yuzaga keladigan ijtimoiy munosabatlar tahliliga bag'ishlangan.

Kalit so'zlar: jamiyat, ta'lim, huquq, huquqiy ong, huquqiy madaniyat

Аннотация: Настоящая тезис посвящен актуальным вопросам повышения правосознания и правовой культуры, а так же, анализу общественных отношений, возникающие по поводу правового сознания и правовой культуры.

Ключевые слова: общество, образование, право, правосознание, правовая культура

Abstract: This thesis is devoted to current issues of increasing legal awareness and legal culture, as well as the analysis of social relations arising in relation to legal awareness and legal culture.

Key words: society, education, law, legal awareness, legal culture

Legal culture is the most multifaceted and little-studied phenomenon in life. Considering that this is a new direction of research in jurisprudence, maximum connected with legal culture and legal consciousness, it must be said that legal culture and legal consciousness are independent elements of civil society and the rule of law.

The concepts we are considering generally reflect the internal, mental and spiritual aspects of society, the state of development of law, legal relations, legality and law and order, law-making, law enforcement and any other legal activity. In essence, legal culture and legal consciousness are very similar, only in the first case we are talking about the level of knowledge of law, the way of behavior of an individual, and in the second case - about the level of development of society, awareness of the role of law and legal literacy in a more global sense. The concepts under consideration are closely related to such development features as socio-cultural, historical types of various ethnic groups,

social stability and law and order. At the same time, it is by legal culture that the state of development of society of a particular state is very often assessed.

Considering the legal consciousness of citizens and legal culture in the theoretical and legal aspect, it can be noted that it is inextricably linked with legal culture. This thesis can also be supplemented by the fact that science has well developed the categories of "legal consciousness" and "legal science" as objective factors of the legal life of people, at the same time, all this work allows us to turn to the inner world of a person, and determine its subjective component in behavior.

Scientists note that the ambiguity of understanding legal consciousness and legal culture leads to a confusion of the content of the category of legal consciousness with concepts reflecting various aspects and elements of legal regulation. Legal consciousness seems to exist as an independent legal phenomenon, but at the same time it is not possible to clearly distinguish it from other legal phenomena. The lack of certainty in understanding the category of legal consciousness, the infinitely broad interpretation of its content ultimately lead the theory of law to obvious logical contradictions. Previously, the category of legal consciousness was mainly derived by deduction from the philosophical category of public consciousness. However, with all the advantages of this path, it conceals the danger of underestimating the circumstance that public consciousness in itself is not the source or basis of legal consciousness. Scientists note that a theoretical and legal analysis of the processes of formation and development of legal consciousness is possible only taking into account the multifactorial changes occurring in modern society.

For any science, the development of specific concepts and definitions will be practically useful and in demand. It is in view of this task that scientists propose to understand legal consciousness as "a set of views, beliefs, assessments, ideas about law and legality, inherent in society as a whole or a specific individual. Also, it should be added that the concepts under consideration include such indicators as the level of knowledge of the law, the degree of its approval by citizens, the development of skills in legal regulation". [3]

Favorable trends in the development of public relations and the determination of the effectiveness of interactions between citizens are closely related to the increase in the level of legal knowledge.

The reforms carried out in the Republic of Uzbekistan are aimed at implementing the main provisions of the "Development Strategy of the New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026", aimed at improving the public administration system, which involves "the introduction of effective mechanisms for dialogue with the people; the development of modern forms of public control, the development of civil society institutions, increasing their social and political activity" [1], etc. The essence of the reforms is expressed in the main principle "It is not the people who should serve government bodies, but government bodies should serve the people" [2].

One must agree with the opinion of some scientists that "today in legal science the most common approach to defining legal consciousness is its interpretation as a set of views, assessments and emotions, through which the attitude of a person and public associations to the current law is expressed" [4]

According to O. Skakun, "legal consciousness directs it to certain changes in the legal environment, predicts and models them" [5]. The rationality of this opinion leaves no doubt. But it should be noted that the legal consciousness is excessively applied, since not in every life situation and not in every person does legal consciousness allow one to foresee and compare everything. Accordingly, this opinion is correct only for certain life situations and types of behavior.

Other scientists believe (A. Kolotov) that "with the length and multifaceted nature of studies of legal consciousness, the content of this category still remains rather vague and intersects with the content of other concepts and categories of the theory of law. Normative and regulatory properties and functions are often attributed to legal consciousness; the formation of legal order is often indicated as the goals of legal consciousness" [6], etc. However, it must be recognized that the lack of clarity in the understanding of the category of legal consciousness, the infinitely broad interpretation of its content ultimately lead the theory of law to obvious logical contradictions" [7]. Domestic scientist I.V. Kudryavtsev emphasizes the special role of legal consciousness and legal culture as the "basis" for the development of civil society. The scientist expresses a liberal and at the same time meaningful position regarding the views of scientists on the modern development of the concepts under consideration [8].

In the scientific sense, "the category of legal consciousness was mainly derived by deduction from the philosophical category of public consciousness. However, with all the advantages of this path, it contains the danger of underestimating the fact that public consciousness in itself is not the source or basis of legal consciousness. It should also be noted that a theoretical and legal

analysis of the processes of formation and development of legal consciousness is possible only by taking into account the multifactorial nature of the changes taking place in modern society" [9].

Thus, we can make a short conclusion that legal awareness and legal culture are complex and multifaceted social institutions formed due to the development of psychology and law. The legislator in this matter tries not to miss the implementation of tasks in the sphere of increasing legal culture, but often the legal awareness of each citizen remains outside the scope of attention, because for each person to carry out this or that event will rather be not practical, but labor-intensive. In view of this, the mass character of increasing legal culture is justified, and in some part the improvement of legal awareness of citizens by improving individual aspects of their lives (education, labor activity, improvement of guarantees of other social and economic rights of citizens).

We should agree with the opinion of domestic scientists that it seems important to "also pay attention to the psychology of a person, as an individual who has his own category of needs in life. Very often we have to admit that a person is ready to adapt to certain rules of life (including legal norms), if certain comfortable conditions are created for him (for his development). Here, a system of mutual consideration of the interests of the state and society works. Achieving a balance in this work will allow more effectively to promote the values of law among society, explaining the law and the entire system of legislation primarily as incentives to ensure citizens a decent and prosperous life."

It is very important to distinguish between the concepts of "conditions" and "incentives" [10]. "Incentives should be benefits, improvements in material or other conditions, a call from society to help strengthen law and order. Conditions should be formed based on the state's ability to ensure a decent life for citizens. All these factors taken together would allow for a constant increase in citizens' legal awareness, starting from an early age" [11].

In general, agreeing with the opinions of scientists, it should be added that, nevertheless, in legal science, in a certain sense, modern trends in the development of legal consciousness and legal culture have not been developed. Each scientist has his own position on these concepts, which may sometimes contradict the position of another scientist. And all state activity in the field of raising the legal culture of society is aimed mainly at conducting educational events, growing spiritual and cultural principles, without studying the material and urgent needs of life of society. It would be fair to note that this problem

exists not only in the Republic of Uzbekistan, but also in many other countries. At the same time, we do not defend the idea of an "unlimited" way to satisfy absolutely all the needs of the very essence of man, because this is impossible. But at the same time, many socio-economic aspects of the lives of citizens need to be improved, which, in our opinion, will have a favorable effect on the level of the legal culture of society.

A person without legal awareness will live by his own arbitrariness and tolerate arbitrariness from others. In this regard, it is very important to give a new meaning to the concept of "legal education" as a purposeful, controlled and deliberate process of influencing people's consciousness in order to achieve a high level of legal awareness and legal culture [12].

In formulating conclusions on this scientific thesis, we propose to highlight a number of proposals for improving the legal consciousness and legal culture of citizens of the republic:

- it is necessary to expand and improve legal education in the Republic of Uzbekistan using ICT capabilities;
- legal education and all activities to improve legal culture in society should be specific, targeted and focused on society (especially young people);
- legal education should be organized and financially supported by the state;
- the effectiveness of legal education can be ensured by studying the actual achieved results of work with society in general and individually and in comparison with the problems existing in this area;
- legal culture should be promoted in society as a socially and economically advantageous option for behavior in society.

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